

PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS TO WORK WITH GIFTED STUDENTS BASED ON THE ENRICHMENT APPROACH

O.T. Karimov

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute Department of Organization of Scientific Research Activities
of Talented Students 1st Category Engineer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14956854>

Abstract. *This article discusses the specific features of gifted students, creating conditions for their education, and the importance of the enrichment approach used in practice worldwide in working with gifted students. It also discusses attitudes towards some aspects of gifted students, methods of working with gifted students, and parents' attitudes towards gifted students based on a questionnaire taken from future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *gifted student, enrichment approach, individual work, conflict situation, non-traditional lesson, intellectual need.*

The most important and central issue of innovative activity in pedagogy is the effective and high-quality organization of the educational process. In today's pedagogy, there are various methods of teaching and upbringing. The teacher seeks to achieve his goal in whatever way he teaches, and in this regard, he uses traditional teaching methods and innovative methods. Traditional teaching methods have been showing their effectiveness so far, and today's teachers are striving to achieve even better results by teaching in a new way - innovative teaching methods. Innovation in innovative activity is a factor in enriching and developing the theory and practice of education and upbringing by introducing previously unknown changes in the educational process [1]. It is also necessary to effectively use innovative methods in preparing students for work with gifted students based on the enrichment approach. **Enrichment** is an English word that means "enrichment". This approach, which translates into Russian as "nakopitelnogo", "obogasheniye", is aimed at enriching the student's knowledge, supporting his abilities, and revealing the student's existing talents as much as possible during the educational process. A gifted student shows his talents not in traditional classes, but in classes that he has not heard of, seen, or participated in before.

A survey was conducted with 400 prospective primary school teachers to determine which method is most successful for working with gifted students. 48% of the students who participated in the study - 192 - preferred "Individual work." "Working in a small group, with 2-3 students" was preferred by 152 - 38% of students.

1.	What method would you choose when working with a gifted student?	Answer
A)	Individual work	192
B)	Working in a small group, with 2-3 students	152
C)	Working during a regular lesson	52
D)	Another answer:	8

"Working with gifted students in the regular classroom" was approved by 13% - 52 students. 4 of the survey participants - 1% - did not know which method to choose when working with gifted students.

As a conclusion to this question and answer, it can be said that a gifted student, due to his “mysteriousness” and “shyness”, prefers to work individually, alone with a teacher. In this process, the teacher should try to study the interests of the gifted student more deeply, and should emphasize that this interest is “new”. Working with students in the same field of interest, that is, “working in a narrow circle, with 2-3 students”, also helps to reveal and enrich talent, therefore, exchanging ideas, learning from a peer with higher knowledge and interests than him is a unique quality for a gifted student. “Working in the ordinary lesson process” does not satisfy gifted students and can distract other students from the general lesson and lead to conflict situations.

Conflict situations are not “alien” for gifted students. Because the “curiosity” inherent in gifted students often leads to conflicts and “quarrels.” However, only 4% - 16 students - approved the answer to item a) of our question “How does a gifted student behave in a conflict situation?” - “He gets into a conflict situation and gets into a fight.” The opposite answer, “He stays away from conflict situations, does not get into a fight,” was chosen by 176 - 44% of students, while the similar answer “He tries to avoid conflict situations” was approved by 180 - 45% of students.

2.	How does a gifted student behave in a conflict situation?	Answer
A)	Gets into a conflict situation and starts an argument	16
B)	Tries to avoid a conflict situation	180
C)	Stays away from a conflict situation, doesn't argue	176
D)	Another answer:	28

Regarding conflict situations, 20 students (5%) in addition to the above answers expressed the following opinions: “Depending on their abilities, they may react differently to a conflict situation,” “They begin to resolve (eliminate) the conflict situation,” “They listen and express their opinion once,” and “They may or may not quarrel.” 8 students (2%) could not express an opinion on how a gifted student behaves in a conflict situation.

Based on the results of our research, we can say that most gifted students “get into a conflict situation and get into an argument.” Or, as some students added, “He listens and expresses his opinion once,” and whether the opinion is accepted or not is “unimportant” for a gifted student, and he remains in his own opinion. It is clear from this that it is necessary to work with a gifted student in a conflict situation very carefully. If a gifted student has a wrong opinion in a conflict situation, it is necessary to explain it very skillfully and correctly, or to get out of the situation with the task “We will not think about this issue separately, you should also think about it.” In addition, it is necessary to ask the student’s parents for help in resolving conflict and problematic situations. Because for primary school students, parents are still the main characters to learn from. But it must be admitted that not all parents have the same positive attitude towards their children's education. In order for students to demonstrate their talents, the cooperation of teachers with parents is of particular importance. That is why we asked future primary school teachers the question: "What do you think about the attention of parents to gifted students?"

The answer to this question, a) "The student's talent is under the constant attention of his parents", was chosen by 78% of the study participants - 312 students. 7% of the students - 28 students chose the answer "The student's parents do not know about his talent".

3.	What do you think about the attention parents give to gifted students?	Answer
A)	The student's talent is under the constant attention of his parents	312
B)	Sometimes they get interested	56
V)	The student's parents do not know about his talent	28

G)	Another answer:	4
----	-----------------	---

The answer that parents are "sometimes interested" in their children's talents was approved by 56 students, or 14%. 1% of students could not express an opinion on their parents' attitude towards gifted children.

When talking to parents of gifted children, they emphasize that they want their children to be the best in all areas. For example, a mother may ask: "Why doesn't my child want to study if he is so talented?" Sometimes there are situations when parents force their child to do an activity too much, which can lead to a child's aversion to it, because at the same time the child may be interested in other activities. After a while, the child will become interested in this activity on their own. Psychologists emphasize that if the intellectual or motor needs of a gifted child are not satisfied for a long time, this can damage the child's emotions and lead to a neurosis [2]. That is why it is important for a primary school teacher to maintain close contact with parents to support and enrich the talents of their gifted students.

E.E. Antonova, Professor of Zhytomyr State University of Ukraine named after Ivan Franko, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, expressed her opinion on the support of talented people in her scientific research:

- Almost every person is talented, but everyone is talented in their own way. The teacher's task is to help the developing individual identify and develop his or her outstanding abilities and talents.

- Future teachers learn to identify and develop the talents of students by realizing their own capabilities in the educational process. After all, a gifted student begins with a gifted teacher (intelligence is sharpened by intelligence, character is formed by character, personality is formed by personality), - he emphasizes [3]. Therefore, the development of an educational project based on the methodology of preparing students to work with gifted students based on the enrichment approach is a requirement of the time.

When preparing students to work with gifted students based on the enrichment approach, it is necessary to pay attention to non-traditional - non-standard lessons. Because a gifted student expects something new and different from each lesson. Therefore:

1. Lessons in the form of competitions and games: contests, tournaments, relay races, "duel", KVN, role-playing games, crosswords, quizzes.

2. Lessons based on forms, genres and methods of work that are not known in social practice: research, invention, analysis of primary sources, commentary, "Brainstorming", interviews, reports, reviews.

3. Lessons reminiscent of the oral form of communication: "Press conference", auction, rally, debate, teleconference, "live newspaper", oral journal.

4. Lessons based on non-traditional organization of educational material: wisdom lessons, open confession, "the double begins to act" lesson.

5. Imagination lessons: fairy tale lesson, gift lesson, 21st century lesson.

6. Lessons based on the activities of institutions and organizations: court, investigation, patent bureau, scientific council, editorial board, farming [4].

Education is a long-term process and it shows its effectiveness over the years, in different situations and circumstances. Considering that each person has his own unique behavior, we feel that working with gifted students is even more complicated. Because a gifted student is fundamentally different from an ordinary student, he evaluates each event with a special look.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhimova A.F. Advantages of using new pedagogical technologies in science. <https://zenodo.org/records/5919872>
2. Asranbayeva M.Kh. et al. Child psychology and psychodiagnostics. Textbook. T.: “Generation of thought”. 2023. 476 p.
3. Antonova Y.Y. Concept of training gifted students in higher pedagogical educational institutions // Vector of science of Togliatti State University. Pedagogy, psychology. – No. 3 (3). – 2010. – 20-23 p.
4. Ishmuhamedov R. Yuldashev M. Innovative pedagogical technologies in education and upbringing. Textbook. T.: “Generation of thought”. 2017. 116 p.